

MODULAR CREDIT EDUCATION AT THE UNIVERSITY IN THE CONTEXT OF DIDACTIC PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES

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Abstract. *In the system of modern higher education, the entire system is currently being modernized, the emphasis is shifted to the interests of the student in the traditions of the humanistic direction of pedagogy. This is the key feature of the meaning of the introduction of modular credit training. Orientation to the formation and graduation of a professionally competent specialist, highly competitive, in demand on the labor market, means reforming, restructuring the educational process, which is transformed from the process of passive assimilation of knowledge into an active one with the formation of skills for their application in professional life.*

Keywords: *knowledge, pedagogical principles, education.*

Annotatsiya. *Zamonaviy oliy ta'lim tizimida hozirgi kunda butun tizim modernizatsiya qilinmoqda, asosiy e'tibor pedagogikaning gumanistik yo'nalishi an'alarida talabning manfaatlari qaratilgan. Bu modulli kredit treningini joriy etish ma'nosining asosiy xususiyati. Mehnat bozorida talab yuqori bo'lgan, raqobatbardosh, kasbiy malakali mutaxassisni shakllantirish va bitirishga yo'naltirish, bilimlarni passiv o'zlashtirish jarayonidan ularni kasbiy hayotda qo'llash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish bilan faol jarayonga aylantiriladigan o'quv jarayonini isloh qilish, qayta qurish demakdir.*

Kalit so'zlar: *bilim, pedagogik tamoyillar, ta'lim.*

Аннотация. *В системе современного высшего образования в настоящее время модернизируется вся система, акцент смещается на интересы студента в традициях гуманистического направления педагогики. В этом заключается ключевая особенность смысла введения модульного кредитного обучения. Ориентация на формирование и выпуск профессионально компетентного специалиста, востребованного на рынке труда, означает реформирование, перестройку образовательного процесса, который трансформируется из процесса пассивного усвоения знаний в активный с формированием навыков их применения в профессиональной жизни.*

Ключевые слова: *знание, педагогические принципы, образование.*

Introduction: Currently, the modular credit system of education is being actively implemented in higher educational institutions. The relevance of teaching using such technology lies in the fact that the structure and organization of educational activities, as opposed to the traditional system, brings modern learning closer to personality-oriented within the framework of humanistic pedagogy.

The main part: In the system of modern higher education, the entire system is currently being modernized, the emphasis is shifted to the interests of the student in the traditions of the humanistic direction of pedagogy. This is the key feature of the meaning of the introduction of modular credit training. Orientation to the formation and graduation of a professionally competent specialist, highly competitive, in demand on the labor market, means reforming, restructuring the educational process, which is transformed from the process of passive assimilation of knowledge into an active one with the formation of skills for their application in professional life.

The main indicator of the high level of qualification of a modern specialist is his professional literacy, which includes the substantive and procedural aspects of professional competence, and they are transformed into knowledge, skills and abilities. In contrast to the generalized "social order of society" for the training of a specialist, professional competence expresses the real level of training, offers constant updating of knowledge, possession of new information for the successful solution of professional tasks in specific conditions. All this becomes possible with the implementation of a modular credit system, which in turn is based on didactic principles of pedagogy.

Currently, a modular credit system of education is being actively introduced in higher educational institutions. The relevance of teaching using such technology lies in the fact that the structure and organization of educational activities, as opposed to the traditional system, brings modern learning closer to personality-oriented within the framework of humanistic pedagogy.

The theory of modular credit training is based on specific principles that are closely related to the general didactic ones and determine its general direction, goals, content and methodology of the organization. The teacher's function is transformed from a lecture to a consulting one, and the student's share of passive perception of the material decreases, the possibility of its active discussion with the teacher is realized. Then there are stages of intermediate control of the development of the material, coinciding with the end of each block of the module. This control is important for both the student and the teacher.

The next stage: easier mastering of the studied discipline is available by step-by-step study of modules completed in terms of content. And finally, modular learning technology involves the management of the educational process in accordance with the requirements of specialization for the graduate, which can reduce and, sometimes, prevent the adaptation of a young specialist to a specific type of activity, his integration into the professional environment.

Modules, as a rule, are designed as systems of educational aspects with a common feature of compliance with a certain object of professional activity. Modular organization of the content of the academic discipline mechanically transfer sections of the program to the training modules.

The modular credit system in the universities of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been tested to date, the first conclusions on its improvement have already been made. It has been gradually introduced into the educational process in higher educational institutions of the country and, above all, is focused on the continuous improvement of the system of education in higher educational institutions.

The theory of modular credit training is based on specific principles closely related to the general didactic ones used in pedagogy:

independence:

modularity;

conscious perspective;

dynamism;

isolation of the necessary elements from the training content

dynamism.

The principle of modularity is an approach to learning that reflects the content and organizational forms and methods. In this case, training is based on separate functions — modules necessary to achieve specific didactic goals.

The principle of isolation of certain elements from the teaching content implies consideration of the educational material within the module as a single integrity aimed at solving a certain didactic goal.

The principle of dynamism ensures the correction of the content of the modules themselves, taking into account the social order from society. High rates of scientific and technological progress dictate a new value of general scientific knowledge.

The principle of efficiency and efficiency of knowledge. The lack of training with a bias of the applied aspect of the application of knowledge negatively affects the level of professional training of future specialists.

The principle of flexibility implies the construction of such a modular program that it is easy to adapt the learning content to the individual needs of the trainees.

The effectiveness of educational learning processes is influenced by many factors, but first of all, the correspondence of the content of training to the individual capabilities of students.

Analysis and results: The lack of pedagogical skills, the inability to use existing teaching methods and the inability to choose the most appropriate method for these conditions is another reason why the didactic goal is not achieved.

The principle of parity is the implementation of a consultative and coordinating function in the learning process based on the cultivation of an individual approach to everyone. That is, we are talking about a well-thought-out independent organization of the assimilation of new educational material.

All pedagogical principles of modular training are closely interrelated and carry a functional load. They (by the way, in addition to the principle of parity) carry the design features of the content that develop during the implementation of the modular approach in the learning process. All the above-mentioned principles are based on general didactic principles and are interrelated with them. From the above description of the principles of pedagogical principles, it becomes quite obvious that improvement and complete renewal, that is, modification of the educational process at the university are the main elements of the transition to a credit-modular organization of training. It is also important to correctly assess the degree of readiness of the university for such changes that will bring the educational system to a new level.

Conclusion: All pedagogical principles of modular training are closely interrelated and carry a functional load. They (by the way, in addition to the principle of parity) carry the design features of the content that are formed during the implementation of the modular approach in the learning process. All the above-mentioned principles are based on general didactic principles and are interrelated with them.

Module-based learning, taking into account the use of pedagogical patterns in its design, leads to multiple positive effects that can achieve didactic goals, that is,:

- a student who uses didactic materials and instructions acquires greater independence in mastering the subject:
- the teacher's function is being reoriented from lecture to consulting;
- the student's share of passive perception of the material decreases, it becomes possible to actively discuss it with the teacher, cognitive needs are formed;
- there are points of intermediate control of mastering the material, coinciding with the end of each module, which is especially important for both the student and the teacher;

• the possibility of step-by-step study of modules completed in terms of content, based on pedagogical patterns for easy mastering of the entire subject by.

The advantage of implementing a modular credit system is also:

- high degree of academic freedom;
- independent nature of training;
- developing style of cognitive activity;
- innovative content of educational programs;
- expansion of the volume of the university component of educational programs;
- increase in problem-stimulating, interactive teaching methods;
- the predominance of practical forms of conducting classes;
- systematic, step-by-step control of students' academic work;
- productive, research level of knowledge acquisition;
- compatibility with any national educational system.

Consequently, it can be concluded that as a result of the use of modular technology based on pedagogical principles, the student forms in the process of studying such fundamental characteristics that contribute to the fact that he realizes himself as an increasingly independent, self-governing personality. His motivation to achieve success, as well as his willingness to learn, is determined by the desire to solve his professional, first of all, as well as vital problems and achieve specific goals with the help of educational activities.

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